

OBSERVATION AND MODELING OF DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN PARTICULATE REINFORCED MMCS

Nadine Bourgeois, Katell Derrien and Didier Baptiste
Laboratoire de Microstructure et Mécanique des Matériaux, CNRS URA 1219
ENSAM, 151 Boulevard de l'Hôpital, 75013 Paris, France

ABSTRACT

We studied the tensile behavior and damage of an Al-2618 reinforced with 15 vol. % of SiC particles. Whatever the metallurgical condition of the composite, damage occurred by particle fracture. The originality of this work lies in the modeling of the composite behavior by a micromechanical approach. This behavior depends on the plastic deformation of the matrix and of the damage due to brittle particles. The plastic behavior is introduced in Mori and Tanaka's method using secant moduli, whereas the particle fracture is described by Weibull's law. Damaged particles are replaced by anisotropic equivalent reinforcements. The predicted behaviors and damage are in good agreement with experimental results.

INTRODUCTION

To extend the industrial uses of composite materials, it is necessary to improve the knowledge of their performances. So, the prediction of mechanical properties is a subject of first rank. Numerous prediction methods exist, called homogenization technics. The macroscopic properties of composites are estimated depending on the geometry, mechanical properties and volume fractions of the constitutive materials. The finite element method is one of the well-known numerical technics. But, several "analytical" technics are also available, they are based on continuum mechanics solutions and more precisely on Eshelby's results [1].

Many papers deal with the modeling of composite elastic or plastic behaviors [2, 3], but damage effects are taken into account in few of them [4]. Only recent publications [5, 6] turn on damage influence on the behavior of metal matrix composites. The damage approach of [5] uses both the finite element method and a micromechanical model (generalized self-consistent scheme). Our approach [6] is only built on a micromechanical model based on Mori and Tanaka's approach [7, 8].

In the first part of this paper, the materials are described, their microstructure and tensile properties are studied, and finally damage mechanisms are observed and identified. In a second part, we present the micromechanical model, the damage initiation criterion. Then we explain how the broken particles are taken into account, how their effect onto the composite properties is simulated. Finally the simulated tensile behavior and damage evolution are compared with experimental data.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

MATERIALS, PROCESSING, HEAT TREATMENT AND MICROSTRUCTURE

Composite materials and unreinforced alloy were elaborated by spray deposition and supplied by Alcan Int. Ltd. [9] in the form of extruded bars. The composite material is a 2618 aluminum alloy reinforced with SiC particles (15% vol.). The composite material and the unreinforced alloy were both T6 heat treated : water quenched, cold stretched up to 2% and artificially aged at 190°C. 10 and 24 hours were necessary to reach the peak-aged condition in the composite material and the monolithic alloy, respectively. The tensile specimens were then machined in the bars, some were tested in T6 condition and others were then solution heat treated, quenched and naturally aged, and tested (T4 condition). In both cases, T4 and T6 condition, the monolithic alloy behavior is assumed to be representative of the composite matrix behavior.

The particle distribution and geometry (orientation, diameter and aspect ratio) were analyzed by image analysis technics. The particles are almost perfectly aligned in the extrusion direction. Their average diameter is 11 microns, their effective aspect ratio [6] is 1.27. Due to extrusion, the materials are neither homogeneous nor perfectly isotropic. The elongated grains are also aligned in the extrusion direction.

TENSILE PROPERTIES

The composite material and the unreinforced alloy were both tensile tested. The strain rate was $2.3 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The tensile specimens were cylindrical with a 4 mm diameter and a 36 mm calibrated length. Elongation was measured with an extensometer, the strain gage length was 15 mm. The tensile properties of the composite material and the unreinforced alloy, T6 or T4 heat treated, in the extrusion direction, are reported in the Table 1.

<i>(number of specimens)</i>		T6 condition		T4 condition	
In the extrusion direction		Al (5)	Al/SiCp (4)	Al (2)	Al/SiCp (3)
Young's modulus	(GPa)	$73,5 \pm 2$	94 ± 4	77 ± 2	99 ± 5
0.2% yield strength	(MPa)	429 ± 7	488 ± 8	215 ± 2	289 ± 5
Tensile strength	(MPa)	461 ± 7	512 ± 10	391 ± 3	461 ± 6
Elongation at maximum load	(%)	$5,0 \pm 0,6$	$2,0 \pm 0,5$	$16,0 \pm 0,6$	$10,2 \pm 0,3$
Elongation at failure	(%)	9 (2)	4,5 (1)	19,7 (1)	> 11,5

Tableau 1. Tensile properties of the monolithic alloy and of the composite material.

DAMAGE OBSERVATIONS

The damage initiation and its evolution are observed on small polished specimens that are tensile tested in a Scanning Electron Microscope. As the load is recorded during the test the observed events can be correlated with the macroscopic behavior of the composite. Electron microscopy allows to identify precisely the damage mechanism and the instant of its initiation.

In the T6 treated composite material, damage initiated when the applied stress reached the macroscopic 0.2% yield strength. The degradation mechanism was particle fracture. Cracks first appeared in the largest particles or in the most elongated and aligned ones. Cracks were

generally perpendicular to the tensile direction which was parallel to the extrusion direction. The particles failed simultaneously in the zones with high and low volume fraction of reinforcement. So long as the applied stress had not reached its maximum value, damage was spread over the total surface of the specimen. The particles cracked progressively. Then, deformation and thus damage began to localize in a small zone and particularly in areas rich in particles. The localization of damage led the material to failure.

In the T4 treated composite material, damage mechanism was unchanged, but it began largely after the nonlinearity of the tensile stress-strain curve. Damage appeared when the load reached 0.8 times the maximum load (F_{max}), the yield strength is approximately 0.6 times the maximum load. The damage evolution up to the final fracture of the specimen was still the same. The macroscopic and local deformations were greater in the T4 than in the T6 material. Fig. 1 is a collection of two pictures taken during in "in-situ" tensile test, on the T4 treated composite. The load on Figure 1a and 1b was 0.95 F_{max} and 0.98 F_{max} , respectively.

Figure 1 : Damage evolution in the T4 treated composite : a) 0.95 F_{max} , b) 0.98 F_{max}

HOMOGENIZATION, MORI AND TANAKA'S THEORY

Among several well-known micromechanical approaches, the Mori and Tanaka's [7] method is an alternative to find the estimates of elastic moduli of multiphase composite materials. This method has been recently reformulated by Benveniste [8]. The main assumptions of Mori and Tanaka's method were linked with Eshelby's original work [1]. These assumptions are contained in the strain localization relation which defines the load sharing between the different constituents [6]. The localization relation is expressed by

$$\epsilon_r = \text{Tr } \epsilon_0 \quad \text{with} \quad \text{Tr} = [\text{L}_r + \text{L}_0(\text{S}_r^{-1} - \text{I})]^{-1} \text{L}_0 \text{S}_r \quad (1)$$

ϵ_0 , L_0 and ϵ_r , L_r are the average strains and the stiffness tensors of the matrix and the r -th reinforcement, respectively. S_r is Eshelby's tensor of this reinforcement.

Writing that the macroscopic strain (stress) is the volumic average of the strain (stress) in all the phases, it results that the composite stiffness tensor is expressed by :

$$\text{L} = (\text{c}_0 \text{L}_0 + \sum_{r=1}^{r=n} \text{c}_r \text{L}_r \text{Tr}) (\text{c}_0 \text{I} + \sum_{r=1}^{r=n} \text{c}_r \text{Tr})^{-1} \quad (2)$$

This equation shows that the composite moduli depend on the moduli and volume fractions (c_r) of the constituents, and on their orientation and aspect ratio through Eshelby's tensor.

The model is extended to the elastoplastic behavior using the concept of secant moduli and von Mises equivalent stress. This extension was first developed in the case of isotropic constituents and isotropic composites [10, 3], and then used in other cases [6]. The main equations of the homogenization model are unchanged between the elastic and the elastoplastic formulation. If the matrix alone is plastic, the strain localization equation, Eqn (1), is still the same but we substitute the matrix elastic moduli tensor, L_0 , with the matrix secant moduli tensor, L_0^s . Identically, Eqn (2) gives the expression of the composite secant moduli tensor when L_0 is replaced by L_0^s .

Introducing one more relation, which is the matrix constitutive equation, allows to solve the elastoplastic problem. The matrix behavior is identified from the tensile stress-strain curve of the unreinforced alloy. Matrix is assumed to be isotropic and the plastic deformation to be incompressible. The matrix secant modulus is adequate to characterize its plastic deformation. The matrix stress-strain curve imposes the secant modulus evolution as a function of the von Mises' equivalent stress. The composite elastoplastic stress-strain curve is built step by step varying progressively the matrix secant modulus.

DAMAGE INITIATION, WEIBULL'S CRITERION

Damage initiation and yielding can be simultaneous. Then it is of basic interest to introduce the damage effect on the macroscopic behavior of the composite. The simulated tensile behavior, without damage, overestimates the experimental values. Damage modeling includes two parts, the definition of a damage initiation criterion and the introduction of the broken particles.

The choice of the damage initiation criterion is based on the reinforcement nature and ratified by our observations. Let us underline again that damage occurs by SiC particle fracture. Silicon carbide is a ceramic, its behavior is elastic brittle. Generally statistical criteria are used to describe its fracture. And so we introduced a Weibull law to predict the particle fracture. The fracture probability of each particle is a function of its volume, V_r , and of the maximal principal stress it experiences, σ_{rp} .

$$P_r(\sigma_{rp}, V_r) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{V_r}{V_u} \left(\frac{\sigma_{rp}}{\sigma_u}\right)^m\right) \quad (3)$$

This law is a function of two parameters ($m, V_u\sigma_u^m$). It is in agreement with our observations ; damage initiates in the largest particles. The fracture is determined by the maximum principal stress ; the cracks are perpendicular to the tensile direction. The stress in the particles and thus the number of broken particles are increasing functions of the macroscopic load.

DAMAGE INFLUENCE, BROKEN PARTICLES

Damage effect on the behavior is due to cracked particles. It is difficult to really reproduce the cracked particles. We chose to replace the broken particles by anisotropic equivalent reinforcements. The elastic moduli of this reinforcement are still equal to the undamaged particle moduli except in the tensile direction, where they are zero.

$$\mathbb{L}d = \frac{E_r}{1 - \nu_r^2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\nu_r & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_r & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 - \nu_r \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Eqn (4) gives the moduli tensor of a particle containing a crack perpendicular to axis 3. E_r and ν_r are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the undamaged particles. (Eqn (4) was justified by finite element calculations [6]).

Now it is possible to predict the tensile behavior of composite materials, including the damage effect. Damage and plastic deformation vary simultaneously. At each step of the simulation, the stress in the reinforcement is deduced from the macroscopic stress. The stress in the particles gives the fraction of the broken particles for each diameter, Eqn (3). The broken particles will be replaced by anisotropic equivalent reinforcement (Eqn (4)) at the next step. The broken particles are introduced in Eqn (2) as an additional family, a new term in the summation.

COMPARISON BETWEEN SIMULATED AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

MICROSTRUCTURAL PARAMETERS

The composite is assumed to be a continuous matrix reinforced with ellipsoidal reinforcements. As the dispersion of the particle aspect ratio and orientation are not large, it has only a slight effect on the result. The both parameters are assumed to be constant, ellipsoids are aligned in the extrusion direction and their aspect ratio (length on diameter ratio) is 1.27. The particle volume fraction is 15%. The particle size is defined as the diameter of the sphere which has the same volume as the considered particle. We introduce three populations of particles : large, 17 μm diameter, medium, 11 μm and small, 5 μm . Each category contains 20%, 55% and 25% (vol.) of the total particle quantity, respectively.

While the particle geometry and the matrix properties are experimentally determined, the mechanical properties of silicon carbide are not easily measurable. Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio values are quite usually collected in the literature, but the data on Weibull's parameters are rare. Anyhow they highly depends on the type of SiC particles. Therefore we identified them using some experimental and simulated results on T6 treated composite material.

BEHAVIOR AND DAMAGE OF T6 TREATED COMPOSITE

Unknown Weibull's parameters were adjusted in agreement with Llorca's results [11] concerning the particle volume fraction at fracture. The composite studied in [11] was cut in the same bar and heat treated simultaneously to ours. At fracture, when the macroscopic strain was 4 or 5%, 90% of the 17 μm particles were broken, against only 50 % and 10% of the 11 and 5 μm particles, respectively. These values are in agreement with our simulation shown on Fig. 2. This damage evolution also leads to a perfect fitting of the simulated tensile stress-strain curves with the experimental ones (Fig. 3).

Figure 2 : Simulated evolution of the broken particle fraction - T6 treated composite.

Figure 3 : Simulated and experimental composite tensile curves - T6 condition.

The simulated curves, with and without damage, diverge since the beginning of non linear part. This zone is precisely associated with the damage initiation we observed.

BEHAVIOR AND DAMAGE OF T4 TREATED COMPOSITE

Then, we simulated the tensile behavior of T4 heat treated composite material. All the parameters, including Weibull's ones, were the same as that used for the T6 material. Only the plastic behavior of the matrix was changed, T4 replaced T6 constitutive equation. The simulated and the experimental stress-strain curves also are fitted (Fig. 4). As we observed previously the damage effect begins at 4 or 5% strain. In the same way, the fractured particle fractions we obtained are comparable to the measured values [6].

Figure 4 : Simulated and experimental composite tensile curves - T4 condition.

YOUNG'S MODULUS DEGRADATION

The model does not predict only the number of broken particles, but also the consequence which is the degradation of the composite elastic moduli. Crack initiation and opening lead to the decrease of the longitudinal Young's modulus. This evolution is measurable during tensile tests with loading-unloading cycles [11]. Experimental and simulated decrease of the longitudinal modulus are shown on Figure 5.

Figure 5 : Simulated and measured evolution of the Young's modulus with strain.

The disagreement on Young's modulus decrease is probably partly due to our choice of the damaged equivalent reinforcement. Eqn (4) is equivalent to consider that there is no more longitudinal stress in a cracked particle. However it is possible to meet several successive cracks in the same particle. Then the longitudinal stress in a broken particle is not zero. Moreover, it is not easy to measure modulus degradation, the apparent modulus is not always equal to the elastic one.

CONCLUSION

With a micromechanical model we succeeded in simulating the damage influence on the tensile behavior of two composite materials. The agreement between the simulated and the measured stress-strain curves is satisfactory. Nevertheless, the Young's modulus degradation are probably overestimated. The modeling work has been supplied by an important experimental work, behavior and damage characterization, and image analysis. Only average geometrical parameters are really necessary to represent the microstructure influence and to ensure the validity of the simulation. Plasticity was introduced using the secant moduli. The damage description with a Weibull law led to good results concerning its initiation and evolution.

REFERENCES

1. J. D. Eshelby, Elastic inclusions and inhomogeneities, in *Progress in solid mechanics*, Sneddon I.N. and Hill R. Eds, North Holland Publishing, 87-140 (1961).
2. G. P. Tandon and G. J. Weng, Average stress in the matrix and effective moduli of randomly oriented composites, *Comp. Sci. Techno.*, **27**, 111-132 (1986).
3. Y. P. Qiu and G. J. Weng, The influence of inclusion shape on the overall elastoplastic behavior of a two-phase isotropic composite, *Int. J. Solids Structures*, **27**, 1537-1550 (1991).
4. T. Mochida, M. Taya and M. Obata, Effect of damaged particles on the stiffness of a particle/metal matrix composite, *JSME Int. Journal, Series I*, **34**, 187-193 (1991).
5. F. Thébaut, Vers l'introduction de l'endommagement dans la prévision globale du comportement de composites à matrice métallique, École Polytechnique *Ph.D Thesis* (1993).
6. N. Bourgeois, Caractérisation et modélisation micromécanique du comportement et de l'endommagement d'un composite à matrice métallique : Al/SiCp", École Centrale de Paris *Ph.D Thesis* (1994).
7. T. Mori and K. Tanaka, Average stress in matrix and average elastic energy of materials with misfitting inclusions, *Acta Metall.*, **21**, 571-574 (1973).
8. Y. Benveniste, A new approach to the application of Mori-Tanaka's theory in composite materials", *Mechanics of Materials*, **6**, 147-157 (1987).
9. J. White and T. C. Willis, The production of metal matrix composites by spray deposition, *Materials and Design*, **10**, 121-127 (1989).
10. G. P. Tandon and G. J. Weng, A theory of particulate-reinforced plasticity, *Trans. of ASME, J. of Applied Mechanics*, **55**, 126-135 (1988).
11. J. Llorca, A. Martin, J. Ruiz and M. Elices, Particulate fracture during deformation of a spray formed metal-matrix composite, *Metal. Trans. A*, **24A**, 1575-1588 (1993).